

Abstract of the article peer-reviewed and accepted for publication in *Palabra Clave* (ISSN: 0122-8285 - ISSN electrónico: 2027-534X) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5294/pacla>

Title: Communication, citizen participation and climate activism. A bibliometric and narrative review of scientific research (2014-2024)

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Abstract:

Communication in climate activism and citizen participation processes have become increasingly important in the last decade driven by the global climate emergency and the rise of digital platforms as key spaces for social mobilization. This study examines the evolution of scientific research on these topics between 2014 and 2024, a period marked by milestones such as the signing of the Paris Agreement and the emergence of global movements like *Fridays for Future* and *Extinction Rebellion*. Through a bibliometric and narrative review of 255 scientific articles published in WOS, Scopus, and SCIELO databases, the study maps trends in scientific production, collaboration, and thematic approaches within the field. The methodology combined quantitative analysis of bibliometric indicators, including growth rates, publication languages, co-authorship patterns, and collaboration networks, with qualitative analysis of keywords, abstracts, and titles to categorize the main thematic areas. The findings reveal a sustained growth in scientific output, dominated by publications in English and by authors affiliated with institutions in the Global North, reflecting significant structural asymmetries. Thematically, there is a strong concentration around climate communication framing, with a particular focus on youth activism, digital platforms, and emotional narratives, especially linked to movements like *Fridays for Future*. In contrast, approaches grounded in communication process in local contexts, everyday activism, citizen science, and perspectives from the Global South remain underrepresented, exposing an epistemic gap. These results highlight both the growth and the limitations of the field, emphasizing the need for future research centered on local contexts, underrepresented territories, and decolonial approaches to strengthen citizen agency in the face of the climate crisis.

Keywords: climate communication, citizen participation, climate activism, digital platforms, global South perspectives.

Note: The final version will be available in *Palabra Clave* through the journal's website: <https://palabraclave.unisabana.edu.co/index.php/palabraclave>